

Deliverable report for

Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling

Project 101058632

Deliverable n°:	D1.3
Deliverable name:	Data Management Plan
Version:	2.0
Release date:	29.11.2022
Type:	Report (R)
Dissemination level:	Public (PU)
Status:	Final
Author:	Filipe Neves (LNEG)

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Change Records

Version	Date	Changes	Edited by
v1.0	01.11.2022	Initial draft	Filipe Neves
v2.0	29.11.2022	Adoption of the changes proposed by the reviewers	Filipe Neves

Peer reviewed by WP Leaders:

WP Leader	Reviewer
1	Filipe Neves (LNEG)
2	Daniel de Oliveira (LNEG)
3	Alvise Bianchin (MBN)
4	Patricia Carvalho (SINTEF)
5	Maarten den Heijer (RGS)
6	Bruno Vicenzi (EPMA)
7	Luís Lopes (LPRC)

Deliverable beneficiaries:

WP / Task
All WPs and Tasks

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2 ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
CERN	Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EU	European Union
ExCom	Executive Committee
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
IoT	Internet of Things
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ISSN	International Standard Serial Number
KIC	Knowledge and Innovation Community
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Cost analysis
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
REST API	Representational state transfer application programming interface
SME	Small and Medium Sized Enterprises
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

3 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable introduces the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the START project. The START DMP provides an analysis of the main elements of the data management policy that will be used throughout the project by the partners. Specifically, the DMP describes the methodology for data collection and generation and whether and how data will be shared to ensure that the data will be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) for the potential users. This first version of the DMP will be used as a guideline and will be continually updated and enriched throughout START. For example, such updates might occur if other kinds of data will be generated/collected or to reflect changes related to the original planning, changes in data/output access provisions or curation policies, changes in consortium practices, and if any other external factors affect the validity of the present DMP. Each partner is responsible for notifying the coordinator of changes in the data they are collecting during project execution.

This document has been prepared using the template (version 1.0 from 5 May 2021) for a DMP provided under the project reporting templates in the reference documents for the Horizon Europe programme of the Funding and Tenders portal of the European Commission.

4 DATA SUMMARY

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?

The START project will capitalize on already existing data and will integrate them with new data. START project partners will re-use literature data, as well as experimental data previously obtained by the partners, for the planning of activities and for comparison with the generated data. For all available data, appropriate references will be made to authors and institutions.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

Depending on the data source, the START project will handle different types of data. The main data generated in START will be in the form of documents (protocols, reports, articles and deliverables), measurement and sample process data, modelling and simulation data, multimedia data and data from workshops/seminars. The START project will deal with various data formats that can be divided into:

- Text documents (*.txt, *.docx, *.pptx, *.pdf).
- Multimedia (images, video and audio) (*.jpeg, *.tif, *.png, *.mp4, *.wav).
- Numeric data and graphing (*.csv, *.dat, *.txt, *.xlsx, *.opj, *.brml, *.raw).
- Models (Crystallographic information file (*.cif, *.str).

Where possible the data will be stored in a relational database so that its elements can be made addressable and easily decipherable by machine learning algorithms.

Annex I shows a detailed description of the data that will be used during the project.

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project? What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

The purpose is to generate and re-use data that will enable to create a sustainable supply chain and a corresponding business-innovation ecosystem for thermoelectric harvesting products based on secondary raw materials responsibly sourced from within the EU. The generated and re-used data is also needed to address and attain the different START objectives as specified in the Grant Agreement and summarized below:

- *Significantly reduce the import dependency of critical raw materials required to produce thermoelectric devices by substituting a key component (the p-type semiconductor thermoelement) with a component based on raw materials that can be found in significant quantity in mine wastes across the EU.*

The achievement of this objective is associated with the production of data related to experimental measurements, mineral preparation and separation activities, materials processing activities, modelling and simulation, and environmental and economic sustainability assessments.

- *Develop and deploy a novel methodology for the accurate mineralogical evaluation of mine wastes to be used as feedstock in the production process of the p-type semiconductor thermoelements.*

This objective will require the collection, elaboration and re-use of data related with the identification of mineralogically suitable mine waste sites and with ore sampling and mineral separation.

- *Develop and implement scalable and environmentally friendly methods to produce advanced mineral-derived sulphide p-type semiconductor thermoelements.*

This objective will imply the re-use of data from the literature and experimental data previously obtained by the partners, and the production of data from modelling and experimental activities.

- *Evaluate and optimise the overall performance of the new thermoelectric materials to produce reliable and robust devices with the highest economic efficiency, suitable to be applied in waste heat recovery systems ranging from heavy and maritime industries to ubiquitous energy applications.*

For the achievement of this objective, data will be generated from modelling and simulation activities, experimental measurements, and economic evaluation studies. These data will be used to produce prototypes of the thermoelectric generating device.

- *Conduct simulations, experiments and engage with customers to confirm the market potential of the produced thermoelectric devices in terms of economic efficiency and other performance indicators.*

This objective will require the production of data, such as reports, publications, multimedia and demonstrators, which will be used to better understand the benefits of the developed thermoelectric devices.

- *Co-create a new commercial ecosystem with stakeholders and customers along the value chain, addressing market penetration barriers and opportunities.*

This objective will require the conversion of dissemination products and tools (website, social media channels, newsletters, databases, etc) into commercially attractive digital multimedia services.

- *Maximize project results, outputs, and outcomes.*

This objective implies following the FAIR principles for all types of data generated for a successful implementation of the proposed dissemination and communication actions.

- *Foster public engagement activities outside the traditional academic/industrial context and aimed at non-specialists, to improve the public's understanding of raw materials sustainability and of renewable energies and their role in today's world.*

This objective will generate multimedia products and short and easy-to-understand reports.

The size of the data generated or reused will be evaluated during the course of the project and will depend on the extent and nature of the data that will be made available. However, it is possible to estimate that it should be in the order of a few tens of GB.

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

The data generated in START will have its origin in experimental measurements, ore sampling protocols, mineral preparation and separation activities, materials processing activities, modelling and simulation, prototypes and demonstrator devices, environmental and economic sustainability assessments, replication and market development studies and exercises/workshops used to collect data and views from stakeholders. Additional outcomes include scientific/technical manuscripts and presentations, training activities and other public engagement activities. The re-used data will have its origin mainly in literature and existing datasets on mine waste cadastres, geological information, model simulations, thermoelectric materials, LCA and LCC. Data from the foresight exercises and workshops will be obtained from experts and stakeholders.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The data generated during START project will be useful to the following sectors:

- Mining industry. The START approach can prevent what is now considered as waste material from ending up in mine tailings if extracted directly from an operating mine promoting the principles of the circular economy and reducing the environmental footprint of mines and their waste piles.
- All types of industries generating heat, and where waste heat is a significant factor, e.g., metal industry, cement & concrete, biomass refineries, and glass production.
- Business developers looking at new opportunities to invest in ubiquitous energy: to provide power to sensors and IoT everywhere.
- Operators of facilities at remote locations where additional power is at a premium, e.g., long haul maritime transport, isolated islands with wasted thermal power.
- Researchers, innovative SMEs, KICs seeking to join the business-innovation ecosystem to be created by START.
- Governmental bodies for which the published data might be relevant for decision-making.
- The general public to improve the public's understanding of the need for raw materials and understand the concepts of sustainability, energy and circular economy.

5 FAIR DATA

5.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

In accordance with Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement, a persistent identifier will identify the data generated during the execution of START activities. Open START data that are deposited in the START default open access repository (Zenodo, <https://zenodo.org/>) will be assigned a DOI automatically and will benefit also from Zenodo's DOI versioning support. Additionally, open START data that are deposited in institutional repositories, repositories of scientific publishers or other data and research repositories will be at least indefinable by a persistent URL. If the institution is a DOI registrant that has an agreement with a DOI registration agency, a DOI will also be assigned.

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Zenodo's metadata is compliant with DataCite's Metadata Schema (<https://schema.datacite.org/>) minimum and recommended terms. This means that open START data deposited in Zenodo are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes where each record will contain a minimum of DataCite's mandatory terms, with optionally additional DataCite recommended terms and Zenodo's enrichments. At this time, it is not possible to find a metadata standard that fits the different types of data that will be generated by the START project. Nevertheless, the following deposition metadata fields will be mandatory in START:

- Title. Title of the deposition.
- Description. Abstract or description for deposition.

- Files. Deposition files identifiers, filenames, size of the files in bytes and MD5 checksum of files.
- Upload_type. Type of the deposition from a controlled vocabulary (publication, dataset, ...).
- Publication venue. indication of the venue of publication.
- Publication_date. Date of publication in ISO 8601 format (YYYY-MM-DD).
- Authors. The authors of the deposition.
- License. Open license from controlled vocabulary "Open Definition Licenses Service".
- DOI. Digital Object Identifier assigned by the DOI registrant (e.g. Zenodo).
- Keywords. Free form keywords for this deposition.
- Related_identifiers. Persistent identifiers of the related data.
- Communities. Indication of the Zenodo community where the deposition will appear (<https://zenodo.org/communities/start-heproject/>)
- Funding programme. Reference to the funding programmes.
- Grants. Indication of the grants project name, acronym, and number.

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use? Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

All open START data deposited in a repository will provide search keywords together with their metadata. All data deposited in Zenodo are registered and indexed in a searchable resource. In fact, the metadata of each record, in addition to being indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing, is also sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there.

5.2 MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE

Repository

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

The START default repository for all open data is the multidisciplinary Zenodo repository. A START project page (community) has been set up and can be accessed at <https://zenodo.org/communities/start-heproject/>. Zenodo is a European Commission trusted repository hosted by CERN and is compliant with the FAIR data principles.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Currently, there is no need for such an arrangement. Zenodo is one of the all-purpose repositories recommended by the European Commission for projects like START without ready access to an organized data centre.

Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Zenodo repository ensures that an identifier is assigned to the data to make it easily and uniquely citable. Furthermore, a DOI is automatically assigned to all uploaded data, which can be uploaded in any file format.

Data

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

The different types of data that are generated in START will be open by default under a permissive license, such as Creative Commons (CC), specifically Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY-4.0, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode>), to ensure citation. However, the following general exceptions will be applied:

- Copyright and permissions for reusing third-party datasets. Re-used data will only be made open if any of the underlying data is also open.
- Sensitive data will not be publicly available, according to data protection law. The data to be considered as sensitive include those related to chemical composition, design concepts and constructive details of industrial size high-energy ball mills, processing routes parameters and materials concepts produced via high-energy ball milling, thermoelectric materials casting technology, thermoelectric module design and assembly technology, and data driven linked to the commercial ecosystem to be created in START.
- Personal data treatment. Datasets referring to personal data are not open by default as their publication may pose privacy, ethical or security risks.

Moreover, all open data, including reports of public interest and deliverables, will also be accessible via the project website.

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

The decision to make the data publicly available will follow the rules established in section 8.4 of the Consortium Agreement in section 5.3 of Deliverable 6.2 – Dissemination and Communication Plan. As stated there, all partners are requested to be proactive in bringing information about the project, its approach and results to the biggest possible audience. This means that publications are welcome at any time, provided they respect the basic rules that will make them useful for the project's cause.

Each partner must examine the possibility of protecting adequately its results for an appropriate period and with appropriate territorial coverage, if (a) the results can reasonably be expected to be commercially or industrially exploited, and if (b) protecting them is possible, reasonable and justified. When deciding on protection, the partner must consider its own legitimate interests and the legitimate interests (especially commercial) of other partners. Consequently, a data embargo will be employed during the reviewing process for making the data publicly available and during the patent application process for patents until a patent has been granted. This also implies that relevant data necessary for the verification of results that are publicly available will only be accessible on the START default repository after it has been checked that there are no intellectual property issues. In addition, if a specific process is being tested for commercialized use without

being patented, data embargo may apply. After protection of inventions through a granted patent, data will be made available.

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

The files can be downloaded from the data repository via HTTP protocol using a standard web browser. In Zenodo, data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol:

- Data for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name.
- Data is also retrievable through the public REST API.

OAI-PMH and REST are open, free and universal protocols for information retrieval on the web.

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project? How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

In cases where a restriction on open access to data is necessary, this does not imply a total embargo as mechanisms will be provided for making data available under controlled conditions. For example, for the data deposited in Zenodo under an embargo status it will be provided an end date for that embargo, which will restrict access to the data until the end of the embargo period. After that period, the content will become publicly available automatically. In Zenodo, data can be accessed anonymously. In addition, granting access during the embargo period to any individuals who wish to access the restricted data will be done upon request.

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g., to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

At this stage, we do not foresee the need for a data access committee. In case these issues arise, START ExCom board can act as data access committee and seek clarification.

Metadata

Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

All metadata will be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0 and will contain enough information (direct link) to enable the user to access the data.

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

All publicly released data deposited in the Zenodo repository will be available for at least 5 years after project completion. According to Zenodo's general policies concerning the retention period (<http://about.zenodo.org/policies/>), "items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least."

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Currently, we do not anticipate the need for any specific software to access the data, as the data will be shared using standard formats.

5.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

Zenodo, the START default repository, is not a domain-specific repository, yet through compliance with DataCite's Metadata Schema, metadata meets one of the broadest cross-domain standards available. Additionally, we will follow the recommendations of the dataset repository adding the appropriate metadata to make the data interoperable.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

This will be addressed over the course of the project and if necessary additional details will be reported in future versions of the DMP.

Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

The data generated in START will include qualified references to other data, where each referenced external piece of data will be qualified by one (or more) resolvable persistent identifier (such as URL, DOI, ISSN, ISBN, etc.).

5.4 INCREASE DATA RE-USE

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

All relevant data necessary for the verification and validation of results that are publicly available will be accessible on the START default repository, Zenodo, after it has been checked that there are no intellectual property issues. If there are restrictions, access to individuals with legitimate interest will be evaluated and granted on request.

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

The START default repository, Zenodo, is a multi-disciplinary free to upload and free to access database platform accessible from any internet connection public, private or institutional. Data is accessed through an easy-to-use web interface, so no special tools are required to access or read the data. As already mentioned in 5.2, the publicly released data produced in START will be licensed under Creative Commons (CC), specifically Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

International (CC-BY-4.0, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode>), to ensure citation.

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

The publicly released data produced in START are useable for third parties, also after the end of the project. The documentation and metadata of each dataset recognize the data provenance through proper citation of the source of information using the formats usually accepted by the relevant scientific community.

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

Different quality assurance processes will be applied depending on the nature of the data. For example, all deliverables are subject to internal peer review before the submission to the granting authority, as described in Deliverable 6.2 – Dissemination and Communication Plan, and for finding suitable open access publishers, partners are encouraged to consult the Directory of Open Access Journals (<https://doaj.org/>), a service that indexes high quality, peer-reviewed open access academic journals that use an appropriate quality control system.

6 OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g., software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g., new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

Other research outputs to be generated in START are expected to be workflows, protocols, models, mineral samples, new thermoelectric materials, thermoelectric generator device demonstrator, and multimedia.

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

In line with the FAIR principles, the other research outputs mentioned above will be shared and opened as early as possible, following the same guidance as described previously in section 5.

7 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?

No costs are foreseen for storing, sharing and preserving the START open data in the project's default repository (Zenodo). However, some partners may decide to publish their data in full open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications, where a cost is associated. Additional details will be reported, as needed, in future versions of the DMP.

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

For cases where data will be published in full open access peer review journals, the one-time journal open access fees will be paid directly by each partner using the START budget, as this type of publication fee are eligible for reimbursement, as stated in Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

The project coordinator, LNEG, is responsible of START data management, and there is a specific task (Task 3.1 - Data Management, Monitoring of Project Activities and Reporting) for that purpose in WP1 (Coordination and management). Thus, the project coordinator is responsible for:

- The development, implementation and monitoring of the data management.
- Writing the DMP.
- Providing support and solutions for specific issues related with the DMP.

Considering that data management activities are linked to the whole project implementation, the WP leaders have also responsibilities in DMP implementation. Specifically, the WP leaders are responsible for:

- The implementation and monitoring of data management activities in their respective WP.
- Monitoring that open data are deposited in the default repository.
- Monitoring that open data available in Zenodo are properly linked with START.

Additionally, as data management activities are strongly linked to publication of project results the WP leader for the dissemination and communication activities is also responsible for:

- Offering assistance in choosing the right publication path.
- Monitoring that metadata about publications is made available in the START project area on the Funding & Tenders Portal (preferably automatically through Zenodo) and on the START website.

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

The open START data will be stored in the Zenodo repository for long-term preservation and no costs are anticipated. By using a free to upload and free to access repository, START outputs will be citable, shareable and discoverable for the long term. If needed, additional details will be reported in future versions of the DMP.

8 DATA SECURITY

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

All data, either generated or re-used during the START project lifetime, will be stored on the project's SharePoint site (a Microsoft cloud-based platform), as well as on the responsible partner's storage system. The files will be labelled in a systematically structured way, in order to ensure the coherence of the final dataset. By using a Microsoft cloud-based platform, we are reliant on the safety of the Microsoft SharePoint system. Microsoft offers robust, multi-layered protection for data

security in SharePoint. In addition, SharePoint comes with advanced security features that authenticate users and prevent unauthorized access to sensitive information. Data integrity is maintained by optimizing access to data and shareability and, for example, different security configurations can be set at the document, folder, site or library level.

The START SharePoint site is a private group managed by the coordinator and restricted to the consortium members. To avoid having data storage on laptops, computer hard drives or on external storage devices, the participants will be encouraged to use this cloud server system as often as possible and to transfer the data files via secure internet connections. At the same time, every partner is responsible for ensuring that the data are stored safely and securely and in full compliance with European Union data protection laws.

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

The data generated in START will also be stored in Zenodo repository for long term preservation and curation according to the source of the data. Zenodo is a certified and reliable multi-disciplinary open-access repository, developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN, suitable for long term data preservation and curation. Any other repository options that may be considered will always have to be evaluated by the coordinator, who will decide whether consultation with the ExCom is necessary. After the data has been uploaded to the repository, and even after the project is completed, all responsibilities regarding both storage security and data recovery will fall to the repository.

9 ETHICS

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

There are no concerns on ethical or legal aspects that could have an impact on data sharing.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Although no personal data will be treated during the implementation of the START project's technical activities, the project meetings and general administration (WP1 responsibility), the dissemination activities such as workshops, newsletter subscription and training seminars (WP6 responsibility) and the workshops and foresight exercises (WP7 responsibility), participation in which is on a voluntary basis, may involve the use of personal data. For this type of dissemination and data collection activities that may lead to the collection of personal data, an Informed Consent Form will be prepared and handed out to any individual participant. With this, individuals are informed about the intended use of the personal data collected from them, with which they must agree and give their active approval in the form of written consent.

10 OTHER ISSUES

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

Currently, there are no plans to use any other procedures for data management.

11 ANNEX I – SYNTHESIS OF DATA ITEMS PLANNED BY WORK PACKAGE

Work Package number	Origin of data	Type	Format
All WP	Deliverables	Text, demonstrator, multimedia	*.pdf, *.jpeg, *.tif, *.png, *.mp4, *.html
All WP	Working documents	Text, numeric, graphing data	*.docx, *.pdf, *.pptx, *.xlsx
All WP	Scientific/technical articles	Text	*.docx, *.pdf
All WP	Structured databases	Database	*.json, *.yaml, *.tif, *.ascii, *.hfd5, *.accdb
WP2	Datasets on mine waste sites, mineral sampling and treatment protocols	Text, numeric, graphing data, mineral samples	*.docx, *.pdf, *.csv, *.ascii, *.xlsx, *.jpeg, *.tif
WP3	Datasets on materials production, modelling	Text, numeric, graphing data, thermoelectric materials	*.docx, *.csv, *.xlsx, *.opj, *.jpeg, *.tif, *.ascii
WP4	Datasets on materials characterisation	Text, numeric, graphing data, images, models	*.docx, *.pdf, *.csv, *.raw, *.txt, *.dat, *.xlsx, *.opj, *.brml, *.jpeg, *.tif, *.cif, *.str
WP5	Simulation, datasets on device production and LCA/LCC	Text, numeric, graphing data, prototypes	*.ascii, *.docx, *.pdf, *.cif, *.csv, *.txt, *.xlsx
WP6	Website, Webinars, video content, digital stories, publications, reports, presentations	Multimedia, text	*.html, *.mp4, *.wav, *.jpeg, *.tif, *.png, *.docx, *.pdf, *.pptx
WP7	Replication and market development studies Experts' views and opinions	Text, Multimedia	*.pdf, *.jpeg, *.docx, *.xlsx